

(RESEARCH ARTICLE)

School heads techniques in monitoring and evaluation of Teachers' strategies in public elementary schools

MAY ZEPEDA BELO *

Master of Arts in Education major in Administration and Supervision, Daniel B. Pena Memorial College Foundation, Inc.

International Journal of Science and Research Archive, 2025, 15(03), 001–005

Publication history: Received on 20 April 2025; revised on 30 May 2025; accepted on 02 June 2025

Article DOI: <https://doi.org/10.30574/ijrsra.2025.15.3.1663>

Abstract

This study examined the monitoring and evaluation techniques employed by school heads in public elementary schools in Tabaco City Division for the school year 2024-2025. It explored the level of usage of various evaluation methods, their impact on teachers, and potential enhancements. A validated researcher-made questionnaire and statistical measures were used for analysis.

The study revealed that class observations and lesson plan reviews were universally utilized by school heads in Tabaco City Division, while student performance analysis, learning development application, and assignment alignment were slightly less frequent. Key indicators for these techniques scored consistently high, indicating strong adherence. Monitoring and evaluation fostered reflective practices, improved instructional quality, and strengthened collaboration among teachers. Additionally, data-driven insights supported accountability and professional development. To enhance these processes, the study proposed an improved monitoring and evaluation tool, aiming to further optimize classroom instruction and teacher effectiveness through structured, evidence-based strategies tailored to school needs.

The study concluded that school heads employ various techniques to monitor and evaluate classroom teaching, ensuring instructional alignment and effectiveness. Usage levels of these techniques vary, but their impact on teachers is generally positive. To enhance monitoring practices, an improved tool is recommended. The study also suggests retaining current evaluation techniques, ensuring oversight by higher DepEd officials, integrating findings into technical assistance plans, and implementing the proposed tool system-wide. Future research could explore leadership's role in instructional quality, effective monitoring strategies, and the impact of school leadership on teacher performance in public elementary schools.

Keywords: School heads; Techniques; Monitoring and evaluation (M&E); Classroom teaching; Classroom observation; Lesson plan review; Student performance analysis. Alignment of assignments; Application of learning and development

1. Introduction

The quality of education in public elementary schools plays a pivotal role in shaping academic success and prospects of students. At the heart of this educational system are teachers, whose instructional strategies significantly influence how students learn, engage, and develop critical thinking skills. However, the effectiveness of teaching does not rely solely on the efforts of educators; rather, it is a shared responsibility that involves school heads as instructional leaders. As educational institutions continue to evolve in response to changing societal, technological, and pedagogical demands, the role of school heads in monitoring and evaluating teaching strategies becomes increasingly vital. Ensuring that instructional practices align with national curriculum standards, best pedagogical approaches, and student learning needs are essential for enhancing teacher effectiveness and improving student outcomes.

* Corresponding author: MAY ZEPEDA BELO

As instructional leaders, school heads are responsible for fostering a culture of continuous improvement among teachers. Their role extends beyond administrative duties to include classroom observations, mentoring, coaching, and professional development initiatives that support teachers in refining their instructional methods. A well-structured monitoring and evaluation system ensures that teaching practices remain dynamic, student-centered, and aligned with contemporary educational standards. Through systematic feedback mechanisms, school heads guide teachers in recognizing their strengths, addressing areas for improvement, and adapting evidence-based teaching strategies that optimize student learning experiences.

Ensuring quality education through effective instructional supervision is a key priority in global education policies and frameworks. Various legal bases highlight the importance of school leadership in monitoring and evaluating teaching practices to improve learning outcomes.

One of the most significant frameworks is Sustainable Development Goal 4 (SDG 4)¹, which aims to provide inclusive and equitable quality education. SDG 4 recognizes that strong school leadership plays a crucial role in maintaining high teaching standards. To achieve this goal, it calls for structured policies that support instructional supervision, ensuring that teachers receive continuous guidance and evaluation. By fostering professional growth among educators, SDG 4 contributes to the broader objective of lifelong learning opportunities for all.

Building on this, the Education 2030 Framework for Action² provides concrete strategies to realize SDG 4 by emphasizing the need for comprehensive monitoring and evaluation systems. It advocates for accountability mechanisms that assess both teacher performance and student learning outcomes. Additionally, this framework highlights the importance of investing in leadership training programs, equipping school administrators with the skills necessary to oversee instructional practices effectively. Through these measures, the framework promotes a culture of continuous improvement in education.

Similarly, UNESCO's Teacher Policy Development Guidelines³ stress the importance of instructional supervision as a means to enhance teaching quality. These guidelines recommend the development of fair and transparent teacher evaluation policies that focus on professional growth rather than punitive measures. By providing constructive feedback and resources, instructional supervision can help teachers refine their methods, ultimately leading to better student outcomes. Aligning with these guidelines ensures that evaluation systems are supportive and development-oriented.

The Incheon Declaration⁴ further reinforces the need for strong governance and accountability in education. It calls on governments to implement policies that empower school leaders with the necessary skills to conduct effective instructional supervision. Additionally, it emphasizes collaboration among educational stakeholders—including teachers, administrators, and policymakers—to develop evaluation systems that align with both national and international education goals. By fostering a shared commitment to quality education, the declaration strengthens the role of school leadership in instructional oversight.

Finally, the Global Partnership for Education Monitoring Framework⁵ provides a structured approach to assessing teaching quality at both local and global levels. It advocates for strengthening instructional supervision by equipping school leaders with the tools and training needed to evaluate teaching practices effectively. Moreover, it emphasizes adapting global best practices to specific national and regional contexts, ensuring that education systems remain relevant and responsive to local needs. By enhancing supervision at the school level, this framework contributes to the overall improvement of education quality worldwide.

These international frameworks establish a global benchmark for monitoring and evaluation in education, underscoring the need for effective leadership, accountability, and continuous professional development. They provide valuable insights into how teacher evaluation systems can be designed to promote not just accountability but also instructional excellence, ensuring that teachers receive adequate support in improving their pedagogical skills.

In the Philippine education system, strong legal and policy frameworks reinforce the importance of instructional supervision and teacher evaluation. The 1987 Philippine Constitution (Article XIV, Section 1)⁶ mandates the state to ensure quality education for all, laying the foundation for systematic teacher monitoring and evaluation. Republic Act No. 9155, also known as the Governance of Basic Education Act of 2001⁷, explicitly defines the responsibilities of school heads in monitoring and supervising teachers to enhance instructional quality. This law establishes school-based management approach, empowering school heads to take an active role in ensuring that classroom instruction meets educational standards.

Further strengthening teacher evaluation, the Philippine Professional Standards for Teachers (PPST) was institutionalized through DepEd Order No. 42, s. 2017⁸ wherein this provides structured criteria for assessing teacher performance, ensuring that evaluation processes align with national teaching standards. Moreover, DepEd Order No. 2, s. 2015⁹ institutionalizes the Results-Based Performance Management System (RPMS), which equips school heads with a systematic approach to assessing teacher effectiveness. By establishing key performance indicators, RPMS ensures that teachers' instructional practices contribute to student achievement and overall school improvement.

The enactment of Republic Act No. 10533 (Enhanced Basic Education Act of 2013)¹⁰, which mandated the K-12 curriculum, further emphasized the role of school heads in monitoring curriculum implementation and evaluating instructional effectiveness. The shift to a competency-based and student-centered curriculum has heightened the need for rigorous teacher monitoring, ensuring that classroom instruction meets curricular standards and 21st-century learning competencies.

At the regional level, monitoring and evaluation frameworks are further refined to address region-specific challenges in education. The Bicol Regional Teacher Excellence Framework¹¹ and the Regional Plan of Action for Quality Education¹² establish localized performance benchmarks and policies that guide instructional supervision in the region. These frameworks recognize the diverse educational landscape across schools and emphasize contextualized approaches in teacher evaluation. Additionally, regional memoranda issued by DepEd Region V provide specific guidelines for school heads, allowing them to adapt national policies to local educational realities.

At the division level, the Tabaco City Division has established key programs and initiatives that shape instructional supervision. The Performance Monitoring Framework¹³, which aligns with national and regional policies, serves as the primary tool for assessing teacher effectiveness. Division memoranda on RPMS implementation provide localized guidelines for teacher evaluation, ensuring consistent performance assessments. Additionally, the division's Professional Development Plan prioritizes training programs for school heads, equipping them with instructional leadership skills necessary for effective monitoring and evaluation. Classroom observation tools and Learning Action Cells (LACs) further enhance teacher assessments, encouraging collaborative professional development among educators.

At the district level, District Improvement Plans (DIPs)¹⁴ emphasizes teacher monitoring and evaluation as key strategies for enhancing instructional quality. District-wide teacher performance reports, customized classroom observation tools, and community engagement programs provide additional layers of accountability and transparency, ensuring that teacher evaluation contributes to instructional improvement.

Despite the presence of well-established monitoring and evaluation frameworks, the extent of their practical application by school heads remains uncertain. While policies and tools exist to guide teacher assessment, challenges in implementation may hinder their effectiveness in improving instructional quality and student learning outcomes. Thus, this study and educational quality in Tabaco.

2. Conclusion

Effective instructional supervision is essential for improving teacher performance and student learning outcomes, requiring a structured and collaborative approach from school heads. Global and national education policies emphasize the importance of monitoring and evaluation systems that support teacher growth rather than punitive measures, ensuring alignment with curriculum standards and pedagogical best practices. Despite established frameworks, the successful implementation of instructional supervision depends on the commitment of educational leaders to adapt policies to local contexts and address practical challenges in teacher assessment.

Compliance with ethical standards

Disclosure of conflict of interest

No conflict of interest should be disclosed.

References

- [1] Kimball, S. M., & Milanowski, A. (2009). Examining teacher evaluation validity and leadership decision making within a standards-based evaluation system. *Educational Administration Quarterly*, 45(1), 34-70. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0013161X08327549>
- [2] Kraft, M. A., Blazar, D., & Hogan, D. (2018). The effect of teacher coaching on instruction and achievement: A meta-analysis of the causal evidence. *Review of Educational Research*, 88(4), 547-588. <https://doi.org/10.3102/0034654318759268>
- [3] Wang, J., & Zhang, D. (2020). The role of professional development in instructional supervision and teacher performance: Evidence from China. *Educational Review*, 72(5), 633-651. <https://doi.org/10.1080/00131911.2019.1705245>
- [4] Leithwood, K., Harris, A., & Hopkins, D. (2020). Seven strong claims about successful school leadership revisited. *School Leadership & Management*, 40(1), 5-22. <https://doi.org/10.1080/13632434.2019.1596077>
- [5] Marzano, R. J., Frontier, T., & Livingston, D. (2011). *Effective supervision: Supporting the art and science of teaching*. ASCD.
- [6] Danielson, C. (2013). *The framework for teaching evaluation instrument*. The Danielson Group.
- [7] Hattie, J., & Timperley, H. (2007). The power of feedback. *Review of Educational Research*, 77(1), 81-112.
- [8] Rigby, J. G. (2015). Principals' sensemaking and enactment of teacher evaluation. *Journal of Educational Administration*, 53(3), 374-392.
- [9] Stronge, J. H. (2018). *Qualities of effective teachers* (3rd ed.). ASCD.
- [10] Brookhart, S. M. (2017). *How to use grading to improve learning*. ASCD.
- [11] Tomlinson, C. A. (2014). *The differentiated classroom: Responding to the needs of all learners* (2nd ed.). ASCD.
- [12] Mishra, P., & Koehler, M. J. (2006). Technological pedagogical content knowledge: A framework for teacher knowledge. *Teachers College Record*, 108(6), 1017-1054.
- [13] Marzano, R. J. (2017). *The new art and science of teaching*. Solution Tree Press.
- [14] Anderson, L. W., & Krathwohl, D. R. (2001). *A taxonomy for learning, teaching, and assessing: A revision of Bloom's taxonomy of educational objectives*. Longman.
- [15] Robinson, V. M. J., Lloyd, C. A., & Rowe, K. J. (2008). The impact of leadership on student outcomes: An analysis of the differential effects of leadership types. *Educational Administration Quarterly*, 44(5), 635-674.
- [16] Black, P., & Wiliam, D. (2018). *Inside the black box: Raising standards through classroom assessment*. GL Assessment.
- [17] Epstein, J. L. (2011). *School, family, and community partnerships: Preparing educators and improving schools* (2nd ed.). Routledge.
- [18] Mandinach, E. B., & Gummer, E. S. (2016). *Data literacy for educators: Making it count in teacher preparation and practice*. Teachers College Press.
- [19] Wayman, J. C., Jimerson, J. B., & Cho, V. (2012). Organizational considerations in establishing the data-informed district. *School Effectiveness and School Improvement*, 23(2), 159-178.
- [20] Desimone, L. M. (2009). Improving impact studies of teachers' professional development: Toward better conceptualizations and measures. *Educational Researcher*, 38(3), 181-199.
- [21] Schön, D. A. (1983). *The reflective practitioner: How professionals think in action*. Basic Books.
- [22] Guskey, T. R. (2002). Professional development and teacher change. *Teachers and Teaching*, 8(3), 381-391.
- [23] Darling-Hammond, L., Hyler, M. E., & Gardner, M. (2017). *Effective teacher professional development*. Learning Policy Institute.
- [24] Hattie, J., & Timperley, H. (2007). The power of feedback. *Review of Educational Research*, 77(1), 81-112.
- [25] Brookhart, S. M. (2017). *How to give effective feedback to your students* (2nd ed.). ASCD.
- [26] Wiggins, G., & McTighe, J. (2005). *Understanding by design* (2nd ed.). ASCD.

- [27] Henriksen, D., Mishra, P., & Fisser, P. (2016). Infusing creativity and technology in 21st-century education: A systemic view for change. *Educational Technology & Society*, 19(3), 27-37.
- [28] Brookhart, S. M. (2017). *How to design effective assignments for learning and assessment*. ASCD.
- [29] DuFour, R., & Eaker, R. (1998). *Professional learning communities at work: Best practices for enhancing student achievement*. Solution Tree Press.
- [30] Marzano, R. J. (2007). *The art and science of teaching: A comprehensive framework for effective instruction*. ASCD.
- [31] Hattie, J. (2009). *Visible learning: A synthesis of over 800 meta-analyses relating to achievement*. Routledge.
- [32] Guskey, T. R. (2007). *Using assessment to improve student learning*. Routledge.
- [33] Wayman, J. C., & Stringfield, S. (2006). Data use for school improvement: School practices and research perspectives. *American Journal of Education*, 112(4), 463–468.
- [34] Darling-Hammond, L., Hyler, M. E., & Gardner, M. (2017). *Effective teacher professional development*. Learning Policy Institute.
- [35] Desimone, L. M. (2009). Improving impact studies of teachers' professional development: Toward better conceptualizations and measures. *Educational Researcher*, 38(3), 181-199.
- [36] Borko, H. (2004). Professional development and teacher learning: Mapping the terrain. *Educational Researcher*, 33(8), 3-15.
- [37] Avalos, B. (2011). Teacher professional development in teaching and teacher education over ten years. *Teaching and Teacher Education*, 27(1), 10-20.